

Visual to Near-Infrared Image Translation for Precision Agriculture Operations using GANs and Aerial Images

Marios Krestenitis*, Konstantinos Ioannidis, Stefanos Vrochidis, Ioannis Kompatsiaris

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Information Technologies Institute, 6th km Harilaou-Thermi, 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract

The rapid growth of computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, along with advancements in sensory systems and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), have profoundly impacted various fields such as Precision Agriculture (PA). A core operation in PA for crop monitoring and yield improvement is the combination of visual and near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths using pixel-wise operations known as Vegetation Indices (VIs). However, deploying costly multi-spectral sensory systems limits the scalability of existing PA solutions. Towards this direction, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) can be employed for transforming visual images to near-infrared representations, enabling the utilization of affordable off-the-shelf visual sensors and reducing system cost and complexity. Nevertheless, existing GAN-based methods for spectral domain translation often are limited to colorization models that produce pseudo-realistic images, neglecting the crucial spectral characteristics of the target domain. These synthetic images are commonly evaluated based on their visual plausibility rather than the spectral characteristic's consistency. In the context of precision agriculture, such translations from visual to NIR domain may lead to inaccurate VI calculations and unreliable vegetation health estimation, making the usability of the synthesized data questionable. To overcome these limitations, we propose a model-agnostic modification for GANs that leverages the semantic information of VIs in the translation process. Our approach introduces an additional branch to the GAN architecture, calculating the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) from the input RGB and the generated NIR image. By backpropagating the additional branch loss, our method enforces the network to produce meaningful NIR representations that accurately preserve the domain's spectral characteristics. We deploy our approach on two widely used GAN architectures, Pix2Pix

*Corresponding Author

Email addresses: mikrestenitis@iti.gr (Marios Krestenitis), kioannid@iti.gr, stefanos@iti.gr, ikom@iti.gr (Konstantinos Ioannidis, Stefanos Vrochidis, Ioannis Kompatsiaris)

and CycleGAN, and evaluate the synthesized results on relevant datasets. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method provides accurate and meaningful translations of visual to NIR images. The synthesized images maintain their semantic context under the near-infrared spectral attributes, making them suitable for precise VI calculations, vegetation health estimation, and efficient utilization in relative precision agriculture applications.

Keywords: Precision Agriculture, Generative Adversarial Networks, Image Translation, Multi-spectral Imagery

1. Introduction

In recent years, advancements in sensory systems, computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) have revolutionized various fields such as manufacturing [1], autonomous driving [2], medical imaging [3], human risk [4], environmental damage prevention [5], etc. Sophisticated multi-spectral sensors are employed to enhance the perceived information and capture details that are not enclosed under the visible light spectrum [6, 7, 8]. Moreover, the advent of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) significantly affected the current blossom of AI-based approaches. A domain that has particularly benefited from these advantages is Precision Agriculture (PA) [9]. A wide variety of methods employing the aforementioned technologies have been proposed in the past, for crop quality monitoring [10], crop row detection [11], weed detection [12], plant disease detection [13], etc. In addition, more and more user-friendly platforms that do not require an experienced operator or a UAV pilot are proposed by the research community [14] and the industry [15] for PA applications.

A common practice in these systems is combining visual spectrum data with the near-infrared reflectance to estimate vegetation quality and quantity through specific pixel-wise operations called Vegetation Indices (VIs). VIs were adopted from remote sensing applications and comprise combinations of the captured reflectance at visual and/or infrared wavelengths to enhance the vegetation properties. The exploitation of near-infrared (NIR) channel is considered rather essential. Due to chlorophyll's identities, the radiation absorption is strong for wavelengths corresponding to red and blue color while the reflection is high for near-infrared wavelengths [16]. Thus, acquired images in the near-infrared spectrum provide a detailed representation of the scene and insights regarding the crop health, water stress, etc. [17]. A PA system combining near-infrared and visual channels, through VIs, can provide accurate monitoring of crop status, growth rate, etc.

25 Despite the benefits, the high cost of multi-spectral cameras restricts the adaptation of these
26 systems to a wider scale. On the other hand, exploiting commercial visual sensors reduces
27 the overall cost yet, it limits system’s capabilities since valuable NIR information is neglected.
28 Thus, providing an efficient PA framework, utilizing low-cost visual sensors instead of demanding
29 multi-spectral sources is a task of major interest. To this end, Deep learning (DL) architectures,
30 particularly, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), can offer a promising solution based on
31 image translation, where images of domain A are used to synthesize images of domain B. There-
32 fore, a GAN model that transforms visual spectrum images into near-infrared can substantially
33 decrease the total costs and complexity of PA systems.

34 However, designing and developing a robust GAN model to translate visual images to NIR
35 images is a significantly challenging task, especially when applied in real-world operational sys-
36 tems. For example, a set of visual images depicting vegetation areas and their corresponding
37 near-infrared channel are presented in Figure 1. One can notice that plant instances are similarly
38 depicted as greenish areas in the visual spectrum and whiter in the grayscale colorspace of the
39 near-infrared channel. Nevertheless, NIR images provide a more information-rich representation
40 about plants condition through pixel intensity variations. Assuming a GAN model is deployed to
41 translate these visual images to the NIR domain, it will mainly synthesize NIR-like representa-
42 tions by simply mapping green areas to higher NIR pixel values. However, despite the diversity
43 of the training data, the translation model will probably miss variations in the synthesized near-
44 infrared channel related to the depicted plants condition, since this information is not present in
45 the input visual images. Therefore, the information enclosed in the visual spectrum is insufficient
46 to establish a robust mapping between the two domains, leading the GAN to operate more like
47 a colorization module rather than an accurate translator between spectral domains. As a result,
48 the synthesized near-infrared channel would be a naive pseudo-domain representation instead
49 of an accurate depiction of the scene, that encloses its real spectral characteristics. Utilizing
50 these look-alike NIR representations in precise pixel-wise operations, such as VIs, could lead to
51 misleading results and an untrustworthy PA application. Consequently, concerns arise about the
52 extent to which images synthesized by common GAN architectures can be effectively utilized in
53 practice, where precise processing is required to extract knowledge from the generated data.

54 Aiming to tackle the aforementioned issues, we propose a novel architecture modification to
55 inject field-specific PA knowledge into common GAN networks for visual to near-infrared trans-
56 lation. Specifically, our approach leverages the properties of VIs to force the GAN network to
57 synthesize meaningful NIR images from visual data, rather than simple pseudo-NIR representa-

Figure 1: Example images of vegetation areas in visual (top line) and near-infrared (bottom line) spectrum. Plant instances are depicted with homogeneous green-colored patterns under the visual spectrum. On the contrary, near-infrared representations provide detailed variations in the corresponding image patterns, correlated to plants health conditions.

58 tions, which can be utilized for accurate VI calculations and vegetation health estimation. The
 59 proposed method enhances GAN architectures with an additional branch that fuses informa-
 60 tion from the input visual and the generated near-infrared image by calculating the well-known
 61 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) [18]. The estimated NDVI serves as an ad-
 62 ditional control signal for the generative process, and the GAN model’s objective is updated
 63 to map the extracted NDVI index to the corresponding ground truth, alongside generating the
 64 near-infrared translation. The suggested method was applied to upgrade two well-known GAN
 65 architectures, namely Pix2Pix [19] and CycleGAN [20], and evaluated on two relative datasets.
 66 Experimental results indicate that the additional branch guides the networks to generate mean-
 67 ingful near-infrared representations, that preserve the semantic context according to the spectral
 68 characteristics of the NIR domain, allowing their efficient utilization in downstream PA tasks.

69 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. An overview of related works is presented
 70 in Section 2, while the proposed method and the employed datasets are thoroughly presented
 71 in Section 3. Experimental results and their evaluation are provided in details in Section 4 and
 72 Section 6 concludes the manuscript.

73 2. Background

74 2.1. Generative Adversarial Networks

75 Image translation domain involves a wide variety of computer vision problems such as se-
76 mantic segmentation, texture application, colorization, etc., where an image of domain A is
77 converted to domain B. To this end, various GAN-based architectures [21, 22] have been uti-
78 lized. Among them is the notable work of Isola et al. [19] proposing Pix2Pix, a consolidated
79 framework for image-to-image translation utilizing conditional GANs (cGANs). Wang et al. [23]
80 extended Pix2Pix framework to achieve high-resolution image translation. While authors in [24]
81 proposed BicycleGAN to achieve a one-to-many mapping that, generating diverse images from
82 a single input, contrary to previous one-to-one mappings.

83 The main drawback of the aforementioned methods is that paired image datasets are required
84 for supervised training. Aiming to overcome this, CycleGAN [20] and DualGAN [25] were pro-
85 posed for unpaired (unsupervised) image translation, relying on the principle that translating an
86 image to the target domain and then vice versa should result to the original image. Similarly, Liu
87 et al. [26] proposed UNIT framework, based on the assumption that a pair of images from dif-
88 ferent domains share a latent space where their projection is identical. Similarly, authors in [27]
89 presented MUNIT, an upgraded UNIT framework, capable to generate multiple diverse outputs
90 from a single input. In this direction, ComboGAN [28] and StarGAN [29] were introduced as
91 unified architectures for multi-domain translations.

92 Preserving the semantic content consistent through the image translation process has led to
93 several approaches, oriented by the occasional translation type. For face-to-sketch translation,
94 Fang et al. [30] presented Identity-Aware CycleGAN, a modified version of CycleGAN with ex-
95 tended loss function to synthesize more key facial regions more accurately. Similarly, IsGAN [31]
96 was proposed to preserve identifiable information between photo and sketch domains. Authors
97 in [32] introduced a modified auxiliary classifier GAN (AC-GAN) [33] to translate simulated faces
98 to realistic ones, while preserving the face expression. Huang et al. [34] proposed AugGAN to
99 maintain depicted objects' clarity in daytime-to-nighttime transformation, by combining image
100 translation with semantic segmentation. Lastly, authors in [35] presented a domain adaptation
101 framework to project real images into a synthetic source domain for downstream classification
102 tasks.

103 *2.2. Image translation for precision agriculture*

104 Under the scope of precision agriculture, GAN-based methods for translating images across
105 spectral domains (e.g. visual to near-infrared) are valuable as they can contribute to simplify
106 the employed sensory systems. Yet, despite the wide variety of translation types and methods,
107 spectral domain translation is insufficiently investigated. Initial approaches [36, 37, 38] focused
108 on utilizing deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to colorize infrared images. Authors
109 in [39] proposed a cGAN to achieve thermal to visual image translation. Various CycleGAN-
110 based approaches [40, 41, 42] have also been presented for near-infrared to visual translation.
111 Authors in [43] introduced a method to generate RGB images from NIR and grayscale dual
112 input. While in [44], a semantic style loss was added in the GAN objective for more accurate
113 near-infrared to visual translations.

114 A set of works that combine image translation with precision agriculture attributes has also
115 been presented. Authors in [45] introduced a cGAN approach to generate the NDVI index, from
116 near-infrared input, while in [46] a similar approach was proposed where red channel was provided
117 as input. A cGAN approach was also employed in [47] aiming to synthesize the near-infrared
118 channel from visual satellite images, while the quality of the translated output was evaluated
119 in terms of the fidelity of the extracted VIs. Suarez et al. [48] proposed a framework based on
120 CycleGAN in order to translate grayscale to near-infrared imagery and estimated its efficiency
121 by calculating the NDVI index from the synthesized NIR and the original RGB image. Similarly
122 in [49], a CycleGAN-oriented framework was utilized to estimate the NDVI index from the red
123 channel of visual data. GAN-based [50, 51, 52] approaches have also been presented for data
124 augmentation purposes in PA-related classification tasks. Finally, authors in [53] combined multi-
125 spectral images with a set of VIs to develop a GAN model that generates synthetic multi-spectral
126 data from a noise vector.

127 The aforementioned methods have shown promising results, yet most translations are limited
128 to transferring images from near-infrared to the visual domain or synthesizing the NDVI index
129 directly. A solution for translating visual to near-infrared images would be more adaptable and
130 beneficial for real-world precision agriculture applications, leveraging the low cost and the appli-
131 cability of visual sensors. Furthermore, generating the near-infrared channel instead of a single
132 vegetation index provides a functional framework where the synthesized NIR can be exploited
133 to estimate different VIs, analyze crop status, design field-specific activities, etc. Even in case
134 of visual to near-infrared translation, the majority of relevant GAN-based frameworks mainly
135 focus on producing just "realistic" data and thus operate mostly as coloring modules that naively

136 transport some color features between the two domains. On the contrary, a network capable to
137 learn specific characteristics of the translation space and depict accurately the semantic content
138 of the scene would yield more meaningful results that can be utilized by relevant applications.
139 Although efforts to include field-specific knowledge in the data synthesis process have been made,
140 it remains underexplored in the context of precision agriculture.

141 Aiming to address these challenges, we utilize the semantic information acquired through the
142 well-known NDVI index to develop a robust model for efficient visual to near-infrared transla-
143 tion. Specifically, we propose a generic upgrade for the GAN-based architectures by including
144 a supplementary branch that calculates the NDVI index from the initial visual input and the
145 synthesized near-infrared output. This guides the network to map both the NDVI index and
146 the near-infrared output to their respective ground truths, enclosing vegetation-related seman-
147 tic attributes in the translation process. This upgrade results in a robust translation function
148 from visual to near-infrared images, where the generated output meets the characteristics of the
149 near-infrared domain, providing meaningful NIR representations that can be employed for PA
150 operations. Encapsulating VI-oriented calculations in CNN architectures is not a completely new
151 approach [54]. Yet, the novelty of our work relies on designing a simple model-agnostic CNN
152 branch that can be easily adapted to common GAN architectures and leverages the robustness of
153 VIs to create meaningful translations among visual and near-infrared data, while preserving the
154 enclosed semantic information. Contrary to previous approaches focused on generating plausible
155 PA-oriented data, the proposed method synthesizes accurate near-infrared images that can be
156 fully exploited by field applications. To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have been
157 conducted on the translation consistency of visual to near-infrared data under the context of
158 precision agriculture.

159 **3. Material and Methods**

160 *3.1. Datasets*

161 To deploy our method two datasets were exploited, both of them composed of registered
162 visual and near-infrared images. The first was Agriculture-Vision 2020 dataset [55] containing
163 21061 aerial farmland images of size 512×512 pixels. Each image consists of 4 channels, the
164 RGB bands and the NIR channel. The dataset was initially introduced for semantic segmentation
165 tasks for agricultural pattern analysis, yet its registered multi-spectral data can be utilized for
166 the domain translation task also. The dataset is by default divided into training, validation and
167 testing set, containing 12901, 4431 and 3729, respectively.

168 The second dataset was RGB-NIR Scene dataset [56] containing 477 images of resolution
 169 1024×768 pixels, composed of aligned RGB and NIR channels. The images are grouped into 9
 170 different categories based on the depicted scene, namely: country, field, forest, indoor, mountain,
 171 old building, street, urban and water. In our case we utilized only the images of country, field
 172 and mountain classes, following previous approaches [48, 49] and considering they are more
 173 relevant to the precision agriculture scope, leading to a set of 158 images. Since there are no
 174 training/testing subsets provided, the 158 images were split to a training (80%) and a testing
 175 (20%) set, containing 125 and 33 images, respectively. The splitting process was conducted in
 176 respect to the number of samples for each scene class in order to have balanced subsets.

177 3.2. Vegetation Indices (VIs)

178 The reflected light captured by appropriate multi-spectral sensors can differ based on the
 179 targeted vegetation type and the canopy condition, i.e. moisture and nutrition content, biomass
 180 density, etc. VIs are capable to utilize these captured spectral content characteristics and provide
 181 major insights regarding the vegetation growth. Towards this direction, pixel-wise operations
 182 among the different image channels are adopted in order to enhance the enclosed information and
 183 derive an accurate estimation of the vegetation status. In other words, VIs can be considered
 184 as metrics that efficiently measure the vegetation health via the identification of the derived
 185 patterns, enabling spatial and temporal intercomparisons of the examined area.

186 A wide variety of VIs have been proposed by the research community aiming to improve their
 187 robustness and tackle challenging limitations, such as lighting and atmospheric changes or the
 188 absence of multi-spectral data. Regarding the latter, several VIs have been introduced that rely
 189 only on RGB images such as VARI [57], GLI [58], etc. Yet, the majority of existing VIs are
 190 based on multi-modal imagery [59, 60], meaning both visual and beyond the visual spectrum
 191 components, since crucial information regarding the vegetation condition is captured by the near
 192 infrared light due to its material independence. A well known and probably the most widely
 193 exploited VI is NDVI [61, 60], which can provide an efficient estimation of vegetation health
 194 based on the following pixel-wise calculation:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED} \quad (1)$$

195 where NIR and RED is the pixel value of the near-infrared and the red channel of the multi-
 196 spectral image, respectively. Equation (1) implies the importance of having a vector that cor-
 197 responds accurately to the near-infrared spectrum, since pixel-wise operations are required. By

198 exploiting appropriate multi-spectral cameras or precise near-infrared images simulated by a
199 GAN-based approach, NDVI index can be easily calculated to estimate efficiently the vegetation
200 health. Conversely, the robustness of VIs such as NDVI can be utilized in the image translation
201 task, where e.g. near-infrared channel is artificially generated from an RGB image via a GAN
202 model, aiming to produce more accurately translated data.

203 3.3. Proposed Method

204 A typical GAN-based architecture consists of two main components: the generator (G) and
205 the discriminator (D) network. Assuming $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$ correspond to image representations
206 of domains A and B, respectively, the generator is responsible to translate the given input x to \hat{y} ,
207 a y -like representation of the target domain B , via a mapping function notated as $G : A \rightarrow B$. On
208 the other hand, the discriminator attempts to distinguish real image y from fake images \hat{y} . To this
209 end, the generator follows a typical encode-decoder scheme to synthesize fake images, while the
210 discriminator usually relies on common CNN-based classification architectures to segregate real
211 from fake images. These two components are trained adversarially: the discriminator’s objective
212 is to classify real and fake images correctly, while the generator aims to synthesize images that the
213 discriminator mislabels as real. A generic overview of the aforementioned framework is shown in
214 Figure 2. However, in tasks such as visual to near-infrared translation, this architecture may fall
215 short of achieving high-quality results. The discriminator can consider as real, are structurally
216 correct and simply match the generic color shades of the near-infrared domain. This sets a low
217 challenge for the generator, and thus the backpropagated adversarial loss guides the network to
218 operate as a colorizing module rather than learning the deeper target’s domain characteristics
219 and accurately depicting the semantic content of the scene.

220 Motivated by resolving this endogenous matter, we propose to encapsulate case-specific knowl-
221 edge in the process of data generation. Our approach relies on utilizing the information acquired
222 through NDVI in order to force the GAN framework to learn the attributes of the target domain
223 and generate meaningful results instead of operating as a colorizing module. Figure 3 presents a
224 graphical overview of the deployed architecture. Let x and y be visual and near-infrared image
225 representations, respectively. A GAN network processes the visual input x to generate the cor-
226 responding representation \hat{y} in the near-infrared domain, as illustrated. The proposed method
227 prerequisites the involvement of an additional branch on the model’s generator where the visual
228 input and the generated near-infrared output are fused via NDVI. In specific, the NDVI index
229 is extracted from the original RGB image and the generated NIR channel. Thus, the upgraded

Figure 2: Generic scheme of a GAN-based image-to-image translation framework.

230 generator can produce a dual-modal output, i.e. near-infrared channel and NDVI index. The
 231 extracted NDVI output is processed by a 1×1 convolutional layer allowing some further fine-
 232 tuning on the extracted result. Finally the $L1$ distance is calculated among the extracted NDVI
 233 index and the corresponding ground truth, which can be easily acquired according to (1).

234 Mixing GAN objective with standard losses, such as $L1$ and $L2$, calculated over the generator's
 235 output or extending it with auxiliary losses, is a common approach for more concrete results [19,
 236 62, 63]. Assume \mathcal{L}_{adv} is the adversarial loss of the GAN model and \mathcal{L}_{ndvi} the reconstruction
 237 $L1$ loss among the synthesized and the real NDVI index. The overall objective of the described
 238 method can be expressed in the following generic form:

Figure 3: Overview of the proposed GAN architecture upgrade. For visualization purposes a colormap is applied to the calculated NDVI index.

$$G^* = \arg \min_{G, G'} \max_D \alpha \mathcal{L}_{adv}(G, D) + \beta \mathcal{L}_{ndvi}(G') \quad (2)$$

239 where G^* resembles the optimal solution of the objective function, α and β are weighting param-
 240 eters and G' notates the extended branch of the generator, containing the 1×1 convolutional
 241 layer, that produces the NDVI output. The specific layer is exploited to fine-tune the calculated
 242 NDVI values thus, kernel weights are initialized equal to 1 and bias to 0, aiming to apply small
 243 adjustments to the extracted values while simultaneously improving the model's convergence
 244 (contrary to random initialization). Regarding the kernel size, one could employ wider filters
 245 such as 3×3 , however our intention was to simply fine-tune the NDVI output while keeping
 246 the model capacity majorly distributed over the GAN network. Note that the calculation of the
 247 index as expressed in (1) do not contain any trainable parameters.

248 The updated architecture with the additional G' branch upgrades the generator's task not
 249 only to misguide the discriminator but also to generate an NDVI output similar to the correspond-
 250 ing ground truth. Since the NDVI extraction is based on the generated near-infrared channel, the
 251 minimization of \mathcal{L}_{ndvi} implies the improvement of near-infrared band's quality. Considering that
 252 the NDVI index contains semantic information regarding the vegetation status of the depicted

253 scene, the objective is to backpropagate this information to the GAN model through the \mathcal{L}_{ndvi}
 254 loss, aiming to synthesize near-infrared patterns that capture the spectral characteristics of the
 255 specific domain. The proposed G' upgrade implies the NDVI calculation followed by the 1×1
 256 convolutional layer and it can be directly applied as an additional branch of the generator irre-
 257 spective of the initial mapping function formulation. Thus, proposed method is model-agnostic
 258 in the sense that it is a generic-nature update that can be applied on common GAN architectures
 259 without requiring any model-specific modifications. In the following subsection we provide an
 260 application methodology for two well-known GAN architectures, Pix2Pix and CycleGAN, since
 261 they are considered the basis of supervised and unsupervised image translation, respectively.

262 3.4. Method Application

263 **Pix2Pix** model was proposed for image-to-image translation, where the generated output
 264 is derived from a provided image, contrary to the previous basic GAN-based approaches that
 265 generate images from a random distribution vector. For this objective, a conditional GAN
 266 architecture is employed to synthesize an image based on the source image given as input to the
 267 network. This operation requires paired training data, meaning that the images of domain A
 268 and B have to be registered to the same projection plane. According to the authors in [19] the
 269 objective function is formed as:

$$G^* = \arg \min_G \max_D \mathcal{L}_{cGAN}(G, D) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{L1}(G) \quad (3)$$

270 where $\mathcal{L}_{cGAN}(G, D)$ and \mathcal{L}_{L1} are the conditional adversarial loss and the $L1$ loss between the
 271 generator’s output and the ground truth, respectively, while λ is a weighting factor.

272 The proposed method can simply update the Pix2Pix architecture by extending its objective
 273 function as follows:

$$G^* = \arg \min_{G, G'} \max_D \mathcal{L}_{cGAN}(G, D) + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{L1}(G) + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{ndvi}(G') \quad (4)$$

274 where λ_1 and λ_2 are the weighting parameters of each generator’s branch.

275 **CycleGAN** architecture was introduced for unpaired image-to-image translation, since the
 276 existence of a cross-domain training dataset is not a feasible requirement in all cases. Contrary to
 277 Pix2Pix that requires paired images for training, CycleGAN employs a dual stream of generators
 278 and discriminators, leading to two translators, $G : A \rightarrow B$ and its inversion $F : B \rightarrow A$, in
 279 order to perform the training process on unpaired data. Yet, to ensure that these two mapping

280 functions are bijective, i.e. $F(G(x)) \approx x$ and $G(F(y)) \approx y$, cycle consistency loss was combined
 281 with the typical adversarial loss.

282 Following the formulation in [20], the CycleGAN architecture involves two discriminators
 283 denoted as D_A and D_B . The goal of D_A is to distinguish real images of A domain from the
 284 corresponding that were generated by the mapping function $F : B \rightarrow A$. Accordingly, D_B is
 285 deployed to discriminate real images of B and translated images from $G : A \rightarrow B$. Thus, the
 286 adversarial loss for the two mapping functions is notated as $\mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G, D_B)$ and $\mathcal{L}_{GAN}(F, D_A)$,
 287 respectively. In addition, $\mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G, F)$ corresponds to the cycle consistency loss. To preserve the
 288 color composition between the input and the reconstructed output of the network, the identity
 289 loss was also introduced as $\mathcal{L}_{identity}(G, F)$, leading to the objective function:

$$G^*, F^* = \arg \min_{G, F} \max_{D_A, D_B} \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G, D_B) + \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(F, D_A) \quad (5)$$

$$+ \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G, F) + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{identity}(G, F)$$

290 where parameters λ_1 and λ_2 control the membership of cycle consistency and identity loss to the
 291 overall objective, respectively.

292 The proposed method can be easily deployed by upgrading equation (5) with the addition
 293 of the corresponding cycle consistency loss and the identity loss from the NDVI branches, i.e.
 294 $\mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G', F')$ and $\mathcal{L}_{identity}(G', F')$. Furthermore, the stability of the modified model was increased
 295 by adding in the objective function the $L1$ loss of the generated NDVI index, i.e. $\mathcal{L}_{ndvi}(G', F')$.
 296 Thus, the objective function is updated as follows:

$$G^*, F^* = \arg \min_{G, G', F, F'} \max_{D_A, D_B} \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G, D_B) + \mathcal{L}_{GAN}(F, D_A) \quad (6)$$

$$+ \lambda_1 (\mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G, F) + \mathcal{L}_{cyc}(G', F'))$$

$$+ \lambda_2 (\mathcal{L}_{identity}(G, F) + \mathcal{L}_{identity}(G', F')) + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{ndvi}(G', F')$$

297 where λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 parameters regularize the membership of each loss function.

298 4. Results

299 The proposed method was applied following the methodology presented in subsection 3.4,
 300 leading to two upgraded models, noted as uPix2Pix and uCycleGAN. Both core architectures
 301 were selected to cover diverse solutions for the image translation problem, paired and unpaired

302 tasks, respectively. The updated models were evaluated on the two datasets described in subsec-
303 tion 3.1. Details regarding the evaluation approach along with the acquired results are presented
304 in the following subsections.

305 4.1. Evaluation Setup

306 Regarding Agriculture-Vision 2020 dataset both uPix2Pix and uCycleGAN models were
307 trained on 512×512 images for 20 epochs. For uPix2Pix model, the training process was
308 conducted with a batch size equal to 4 and learning rate $5e - 5$. Furthermore, all batch normal-
309 ization layers were substituted by an instance normalization layer to reduce artifacts and lead to
310 higher quality results [64, 65]. Regarding uCycleGAN, the model was trained with batch size 1
311 and learning rate $2e - 4$.

312 For the training on RGB-NIR Scene dataset, both models were fed with patches of 256×256
313 randomly cropped from the training images. Regarding the test set, 256×256 non-overlapping
314 patches were cropped from each image leading to an extended set of 260 samples. Our initial
315 aim was to create a similar setup as reported in [48] to allow the comparison of the examined
316 methods, yet this was not possible, since there are no insights regarding the splitting approach
317 for the training and testing dataset. uPix2Pix model was trained for $4k$ epochs with a batch size
318 and learning rate equal to 4 and $8e - 5$, respectively. uCycleGAN was trained for 500 epochs
319 with batch size 1 and learning rate $2e - 4$.

320 4.2. Baselines

321 Each of the updated models is compared to two baselines that exploit the corresponding
322 original architecture, i.e. Pix2Pix and CycleGAN accordingly, differing in respect to the domain
323 of image translation. The first baseline, notated as $RGB \rightarrow NDVI$, aims to translate images under
324 the visual spectrum to the corresponding NDVI index. Although this does not involve a visual
325 to near-infrared translation, the objective is to examine if the aforementioned GAN architectures
326 can directly provide more accurate NDVI index estimations, compared to the proposed modified
327 models, while the information of the near-infrared channel is omitted. The second baseline,
328 notated as $RGB \rightarrow NIR$, is utilized to generate the near-infrared channel from the input visual
329 data based on the typical network architecture. Regarding the proposed approach, the domain
330 translation is notated as $RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI$ since it is designed to translate visual to near-
331 infrared images and generate the corresponding NDVI indexes. Training parameters are retained
332 in all cases.

333 *4.3. Quantitative Evaluation*

334 A common practice to evaluate GANs performance is to assess the similarity among the
 335 artificially generated samples and the corresponding provided ground truth. This similarity
 336 is usually quantified with typical metrics such as Mean Square Error (MSE) or Root Mean
 337 Square Error (RMSE), as conducted in previous works [36, 45]. However, such metrics rely on
 338 pixel-wise calculations that discard the spatial dependency of pixel values and thus, acquired
 339 results regarding the quality of the generated images might be misleading. On the contrary, a
 340 more sophisticated metric such as Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) can model more
 341 efficiently the human vision perceived quality by estimating luminance, contrast and structural
 342 similarities among the generated and the reference image. Assuming that y and \hat{y} correspond to
 343 the real and the synthesized image respectively, the SSIM index is calculated as follows:

$$SSIM(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{(2\mu_y\mu_{\hat{y}} + C_1) + (2\sigma_{y\hat{y}} + C_2)}{(\mu_y^2 + \mu_{\hat{y}}^2 + C_1)(\sigma_y^2 + \sigma_{\hat{y}}^2 + C_2)} \quad (7)$$

344 where μ_y , $\mu_{\hat{y}}$ denote the mean intensity, σ_y , $\sigma_{\hat{y}}$ the standard deviation and $\sigma_{y\hat{y}}$ the covariance
 345 of the real and the generated image, respectively, while C_1 and C_2 are stabilizing variables. The
 346 range of SSIM values is $[0, 1]$, where higher value indicates a more accurate translation.

347 In Table 1 is compared, in terms of SSIM, the performance of the modified models to the
 348 aforementioned baselines for Agriculture-Vision 2020 test dataset. The uPix2Pix model exhibits
 349 improved performance over the baselines, resulting in more realistic near-infrared images and
 350 thus, more accurate estimations of the corresponding NDVI indexes. Similarly, for CycleGAN-
 351 based architectures, the efficiency of the proposed approach (uCycleGAN) is clearly demon-
 352 strated, achieving significantly higher SSIM values for the synthesized images compared to the
 353 baselines. Both architectures benefited from the incorporation of the NDVI extraction branch,
 354 leveraging the field-specific knowledge that is back-propagated to network’s generator during
 355 the training process and leading to more precise synthesized near-infrared images. This is also
 356 reflected on the artificially generated NDVI indexes, where the proposed method exhibits higher
 357 SSIM values. Additional insights are provided by comparing the two baselines. One can notice
 358 that $RGB \rightarrow NIR$ translation accomplishes higher levels of accuracy compared to $RGB \rightarrow NDVI$.
 359 This implies the challenging nature of $RGB \rightarrow NDVI$ translation, where the network must learn a
 360 mapping function that substitutes (1) while the information of near-infrared channel is excluded.

361 In Table 2 are presented the corresponding results for the RGB-NIR Scene test dataset. For
 362 both architectures the updated models, uPix2Pix and uCycleGAN, demonstrate higher SSIM
 363 values for generated near-infrared and NDVI output, indicating their efficiency in accurately

Model	Domain Translation	NIR	NDVI
Pix2Pix	RGB \rightarrow NDVI	-	90.79
	RGB \rightarrow NIR	80.49	91.35
uPix2Pix	RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI	82.04	91.91
CycleGAN	RGB \rightarrow NDVI	-	82.54
	RGB \rightarrow NIR	64.65	83.26
uCycleGAN	RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI	73.54	88.18

Table 1: Agriculture-Vision 2020 Dataset: Model accuracy in terms of SSIM (%)

364 translating visual to near-infrared images. In line with the results from Table 1, it is observed
365 that Pix2Pix-based architectures generally yield more accurate results compared to CycleGAN-
366 based architectures. Pix2Pix-based networks exploit the paired nature of the training data,
367 enabling them to achieve higher performance. However, it is important to note that Pix2Pix
368 cannot handle unpaired image-to-image translation scenarios.

Model	Domain Translation	NIR	NDVI
Pix2Pix	RGB \rightarrow NDVI	-	93.91
	RGB \rightarrow NIR	81.37	94.57
uPix2Pix	RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI	82.07	94.89
CycleGAN	RGB \rightarrow NDVI	-	86.74
	RGB \rightarrow NIR	73.96	91.10
uCycleGAN	RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI	77.30	92.52

Table 2: RGB-NIR Scene Dataset: Model accuracy in terms of SSIM (%)

369 To support the exploitation of SSIM metric for the conducted comparison, we report in
370 Figure 4 both MSE and SSIM measurements for the same image pairs synthesized by the baseline
371 Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and the upgraded uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI) model. In the first two
372 columns, it can be observed that the proposed upgraded model produces sharper and crispier
373 outputs compared to the blurry images of the baseline. This improvement is reflected in the

374 values of SSIM index since it takes into account the underlying structural information, contrary
 375 to MSE, which is solely based on the pixel values deviation between the real and synthesized
 376 images. In the third and fourth columns, despite the noticeable lower quality of the baseline
 377 output, this is not reflected in the calculated MSE values, highlighting the limitations of MSE
 378 as a standalone metric for assessing image quality. Lastly, in the last column the generated
 379 outcomes of the two approaches can be considered equivalent, yet relying solely on the MSE
 380 metric can be misleading.

Figure 4: Comparison of generated NIR output. The first row corresponds to ground truth images, the second and third rows contain synthesized near-infrared images by Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI) models, respectively. A colormap is applied for depiction purposes and only. The controversy among MSE and SSIM implies the drawbacks of MSE as an evaluation metric.

381 4.4. Qualitative Evaluation

382 Figure 5 showcases qualitative results of synthesized near-infrared images, using the Pix2Pix
 383 (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR + NDVI) comparative translation approaches. The
 384 proposed method outperforms the plain RGB \rightarrow NIR translation, producing more meaningful
 385 and visually closer results to the ground truth. This observation is further supported by the
 386 calculated histograms, where our method exhibits better matching to the distribution of real

387 images, as evidenced by the higher overlap percentage with the ground truth. In all cases,
388 the uPix2Pix approach significantly increases the overlap percentage, implying that more accurate
389 near-infrared images are generated. Additionally, the synthesized images contain crisper details
390 compared to the baseline Pix2Pix model, which introduces to some extent blurry artifacts.

391 Similarly, Figure 6 presents the results for the corresponding NDVI index. Please note that the
392 extracted index values lie within the range $[-1, 1]$, for illustration purposes, though; a red-green
393 color map is applied in the presented image representations. The proposed uPix2Pix approach
394 demonstrates its superiority in accurately estimating the vegetation index when compared to
395 the RGB \rightarrow NIR approach. The reported histogram overlap percentages in both Figure 5 and 6
396 further confirm that while the baseline model can produce realistic NIR-like images, it tends to
397 lead to miscalculated NDVI indexes. This discrepancy arises from the fact that the translated
398 semantic content of the scene does not adequately preserve the characteristics of the near-infrared
399 domain. Consequently, although the synthesized near-infrared channel appears realistic in terms
400 of color shades, it cannot be effectively utilized for precise operations such as vegetation indices
401 calculation. On the other hand, the uPix2Pix method consistently yields more accurate results,
402 both in terms of near-infrared image synthesis and NDVI index estimation, showcasing its ef-
403 fectiveness in capturing essential domain characteristics and generating high-quality images for
404 precision agriculture applications.

405 Figure 7 presents the same set of near-infrared images generated using both the baseline
406 CycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and the upgraded uCycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI) model. Results
407 in the second row clearly indicate that the baseline method struggles to efficiently translate
408 visual images into meaningful near-infrared representations. Instead, it appears to be limited to
409 a simplistic coloring function that maps RGB input to a convenient (in respect to the objective
410 function) gray scale output. This kind of generic translations are mislabeled as real by model’s
411 discriminator, solely due to the generated color shades resembling the near-infrared channel,
412 without reflecting the spectral attributes of the translated near-infrared domain. Conversely,
413 by employing the proposed upgrade, more robust image translations are achieved, preserving
414 the spectral features of the near-infrared domain, as implied also by the calculated histograms
415 . While the uCycleGAN approach may not match the quality of the corresponding uPix2Pix
416 results, it still outperforms the baseline method by generating more meaningful near-infrared
417 images.

418 A clearer demonstration of the efficiency of the proposed method in synthesizing meaningful
419 near-infrared images is presented in Figure 8, where the corresponding results for the NDVI

Figure 5: Comparison of near-infrared channel generated from different translation approaches applied on Pix2Pix-based models. First row depicts ground truth, second row is for the generated output of the baseline Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) model and third row is for the proposed upgrade uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI). In the fourth row, the corresponding histograms are presented accompanied by the estimated overlap (%) among each examined method and the ground truth.

420 index are showcased. The estimated NDVI indexes of the baseline method are inaccurate when
 421 compared to the ground truth, implying that the utility of synthesized NIR-like data, that only
 422 capture coloring aspects of the target domain, is limited. In contrast, the proposed uCycle-
 423 GAN method leads to more accurate NDVI estimations, further highlighting its effectiveness in
 424 capturing essential spectral attributes for the translation task.

425 4.5. Semantic Content Evaluation

426 To further evaluate the proposed method, we assessed the utility of the generated near-
 427 infrared images in a precision agriculture-oriented application. Specifically, a DeepLabv3+ [66]

Figure 6: Comparison of NDVI index image representations based on NIR data of Figure 5 generated from different translation approaches applied on Pix2Pix-based models. First row depicts ground truth, second row is for the generated output of the baseline Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) model and third row is for the proposed upgrade uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI). In the fourth row, the corresponding histograms are presented accompanied by the estimated overlap (%) among each examined method and the ground truth.

428 model was trained on Agriculture-Vision 2020 training set for semantic segmentation to 7 classes:
 429 cloud shadow, double plant, planter skip, standing water, waterway, weed cluster and back-
 430 ground. The main objective was to provide the synthesized near-infrared images as input to the
 431 semantic segmentation model, which was trained on real near-infrared images. By comparing
 432 the segmented outcome to the corresponding annotated ground truth, we aimed to estimate how
 433 effectively the synthesized data can be processed by a fixed detection model and thus, how useful
 434 are for relative real-life applications. Following a similar approach to [19], we assumed that fake,
 435 yet realistic, images could be efficiently processed by the model. Thus, the specific evaluation

Figure 7: Comparison of near-infrared channel generated from different translation approaches applied on CycleGAN-based models. First row depicts ground truth, second row is for the generated output of the baseline CycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR) model and third row is for the proposed upgrade uCycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI). In the fourth row, the corresponding histograms are presented accompanied by the estimated overlap (%) among each examined method and the ground truth.

436 offers also an estimation of the generated data interpretability and, in other words, estimates the
 437 semantic coherence of the translated outcome.

438 Towards this direction, the generated NIR images of Agriculture-Vision 2020 validation set
 439 were fed to the trained DeepLabv3+ model and its segmentation accuracy was quantified in terms
 440 of Intersection-over-Union (IoU). As the validation process requires ground truth information
 441 regarding the semantic content, it can only be applied for Agriculture-Vision 2020 dataset. Ta-
 442 ble 3 presents a comparison among Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and uPix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI)
 443 models, utilized to generate the fake near-infrared images. Additionally, the results for the cor-

Figure 8: Comparison of NDVI index image representations based on NIR data of Figure 7 generated from different translation approaches applied on CycleGAN-based models. First row depicts ground truth, second row is for the generated output of the baseline CycleGAN (RGB → NIR) model and third row is for the proposed upgrade uCycleGAN (RGB → NIR+NDVI). In the fourth row, the corresponding histograms are presented accompanied by the estimated overlap (%) among each examined method and the ground truth.

444 responding real near-infrared images are reported as reference values. Two different cases were
 445 examined for DeepLabv3+ input, notated as "NIR" and "RGN". In the "NIR" case, we aimed to
 446 directly evaluate the quality of the generated NIR imagery. Therefore, DeepLabv3+ was trained
 447 and evaluated only with NIR data. Since DeepLabv3+ requires a 3-channel input, we duplicated
 448 the single NIR channel three times to form a pseudo-3 channel image. In the "RGN" case, we
 449 intended to assess how well the generated NIR channel integrates with real channels of the visual
 450 spectrum and examine its contribution in multi-spectral processing scenarios. Given that the
 451 segmentation model requires a 3-dimensional input, we substituted the Blue channel of the RGB

452 data with the generated NIR channel as it contains less relevant information compared to the
 453 Red and Green channels in the context of vegetation and agricultural imagery [67, 68]. This
 454 is supported by the majority of vegetation indices, which are based on operations among Red,
 455 Green, and NIR channels [69].

Input	Method	Background	Standing Water	Cloud Shadow	Double Plant	Planter Skip	Weed Cluster	Waterway
NIR	Real NIR	77.23	46.49	30.07	32.80	04.17	35.47	19.74
	Pix2Pix	75.54	24.80	15.52	17.22	00.76	13.56	15.93
	uPix2Pix	75.03	28.40	19.61	18.74	01.17	15.16	08.05
RGN	Real NIR	80.44	55.49	34.24	36.84	07.97	44.90	24.28
	Pix2Pix	77.26	36.33	29.10	26.48	01.89	36.36	24.22
	uPix2Pix	77.02	37.29	30.32	27.62	03.41	37.80	24.43

Table 3: Semantic evaluation with DeepLabv3+ of synthesized near-infrared images of Agriculture-Vision 2020 dataset for the baseline Pix2Pix (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and the updated, according to the proposed method, uPix2Pix model. Segmentation accuracy is reported in terms of IoU (%).

456 Results for "NIR" case indicate that the proposed uPix2Pix approach clearly increases the
 457 segmentation accuracy, implying the overall improvement of the quality of the generated near-
 458 infrared images. In the majority of classes, the reported performance surpasses that of the
 459 baseline method, particularly in vegetation-related classes such as double plant, planter skip,
 460 and weed cluster. This improvement comes with the application of the proposed upgrade, which
 461 encloses field-specific knowledge into the translation process. As a result, the generated near-
 462 infrared images are more realistic, with concrete semantic content that aligns with the target
 463 domain properties and thus, can be more effectively processed by the deployed model. Similar
 464 conclusions can be drawn from the results of the "RGN" input. The inclusion of Red and Green
 465 channels improves the overall segmentation accuracy. However, the contribution of near-infrared
 466 channel remains significant to the segmentation task, and the higher quality synthesized near-
 467 infrared channel from the proposed method leads to higher IoU values.

468 Similarly, Table 4 presents the corresponding comparison between baseline CycleGAN (RGB
 469 \rightarrow NIR) and uCycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR+NDVI) methods. As previously mentioned, the plain
 470 RGB \rightarrow NIR translation of the RGB \rightarrow NIR baseline approach generates pseudo-NIR samples
 471 that match the generic coloring aspects of the synthesized band. However, the semantic context
 472 depicted is incompatible with the target domain characteristics. This discrepancy is evident in the
 473 results for the "NIR" case input, where the reported accuracy implies that there are class instances
 474 almost unrecognizable by the segmentation model. In contrast, the advantages of the presented
 475 upgrade are prominent since it leads to significant improvement in terms of IoU for the majority

476 of the classes. This confirms our initial statement that the proposed method incorporates case-
 477 specific knowledge in the translation process, resulting in meaningful translations of visual images
 478 to the near-infrared spectrum, that can be effectively utilized in precision agriculture applications.
 479 Concerning the 3-channel input of "RGN" case, the proposed method also outperforms the
 480 baseline model. Results indicate the importance of containing high quality information in the
 481 near-infrared band to achieve accurate detection. Notably, classes such as double plant and weed
 482 cluster demonstrate significant improvements with the uCycleGAN approach compared to the
 483 baseline, primarily due to the higher quality of synthesized near-infrared channel and its fidelity
 484 to the spectral characteristics of the target domain.

Input	Method	Background	Standing Water	Cloud Shadow	Double Plant	Planter Skip	Weed Cluster	Waterway
NIR	Real NIR	77.23	46.49	30.07	32.80	04.17	35.47	19.74
	CycleGAN	69.33	21.79	16.56	03.10	0.0	09.21	00.95
	uCycleGAN	75.70	24.39	07.33	22.07	01.06	24.73	14.30
RGN	Real NIR	80.44	55.49	34.24	36.84	07.97	44.90	24.28
	CycleGAN	75.98	15.54	19.51	03.70	01.46	03.34	02.98
	uCycleGAN	77.88	22.24	26.39	26.07	00.11	30.31	22.71

Table 4: Semantic evaluation with DeepLabv3+ of synthesized near-infrared images of Agriculture-Vision 2020 dataset for the baseline CycleGAN (RGB \rightarrow NIR) and the updated, according to the proposed method, uCycleGAN model. Segmentation accuracy is reported in terms of IoU (%).

485 5. Discussion

486 The following section provides some insights about specific aspects and novelties inserted
 487 by our proposed method. More specific, its main contribution focuses on significantly reducing
 488 the equipment costs in precision agriculture systems as a typical UAV setup prerequisites the
 489 integration of an expensive multi-spectral camera or dual RGB-NIR sensors. In contrast, our
 490 proposed solution overcomes such requirements by producing artificial, yet trustworthy, NIR
 491 channels from standard RGB images acquired with simple equipment. Hence, the presented
 492 method can eventually promote the use of cutting-edge technologies in precision agriculture by
 493 reducing the overall costs and expanding cognition capabilities.

494 Additionally, current multi-spectral based PA systems require calibrating and image post-
 495 processing operations to align RGB and NIR channels and provide usable data, necessitating field-
 496 expert operators and limiting accessibility for a broader range of farmers. Notably, our method
 497 generates aligned, ready-to-use NIR data, without requiring the application of a calibration and

498 post-processing process. This approach can further simplify the integration of sensory systems
499 in existing PA frameworks and enhance their monitoring capabilities, as it permits the use of
500 common RGB cameras instead of costly multi-spectral sensory setups with limited specifications
501 e.g. acquisition framerate. Specifically for UAV-based platforms, simplifying the UAV’s mounted
502 sensory system can reduce payload and eventually overall weight, leading to reduced power
503 consumption, improved autonomy and ultimately covering wider areas of monitoring. Overall,
504 the proposed method can enhance existing RGB-only PA frameworks, while decreasing the need
505 for complex, high-cost multi-spectral sensory systems.

506 Regarding PA image-based applications and software tools, the main advantage of our method
507 is enabling the acquisition of multi-spectral VIs based only on RGB data. Contrary to typical
508 image translation techniques, our method provides accurate NIR data, that can be safely used for
509 VI calculations. The generated NIR channel, combined with corresponding multi-spectral VIs can
510 be utilized for relevant operations such as plant stress detection, vegetation health monitoring,
511 soil and moisture analysis, yield prediction, fertilizer usage optimization, etc. Additionally,
512 the presented method can be deployed to process historical RGB data and generate missing
513 NIR channel, providing the opportunity to further analyze past data for trends and patterns.
514 Furthermore, a major advantage of our method is its flexibility to utilize different vegetation
515 indices by simply changing Equation (1), allowing to control the translation process according to
516 case-specific requirements. The above can enable the research community to deepen the analysis
517 of various aspects regarding vegetation health, soil management, ecosystem sustainability, climate
518 change, etc.

519 Our method holds value also for the computer vision and machine learning community, par-
520 ticularly in the fields of image translation and generative AI, where we expect it to inspire
521 further research into improving translation accuracy. In addition, researchers can deploy the
522 proposed translation method to create NIR data from existing RGB databases, leading to en-
523 hanced datasets for corresponding downstream deep learning tasks. Even if the translated NIR
524 data are not entirely accurate, the proposed method could be exploited to produce an additional
525 supplementary image channel for relative data augmentation and enhancing techniques.

526 Nevertheless, our method displays some limitations. As a generic drawback of AI approaches,
527 the method requires a large amount of RGB-NIR data to be utilized towards an increased per-
528 formance. Although accessibility to big datasets is improving, obtaining an adequate amount
529 of data tailored to specific crop characteristics remains a challenge. Also, efficiently generating
530 NIR data over different crops and capturing conditions is a complex task and may require further

531 fine-tuning and readjustments of the deployed models. Despite these challenges, we consider our
532 method as a significant promise for precision agriculture domain. It can contribute to derive
533 cost-effective, accessible, and scalable solutions to enhance crop monitoring and management,
534 leading to more efficient and sustainable farming practices.

535 **6. Conclusions**

536 Despite the wide variety of GAN-based approaches for image translation from visual to near-
537 infrared data, in many cases the synthesized near-infrared images are simply a colorized represen-
538 tation of the provided visual input, lacking the special characteristics of the target domain. This
539 limitation becomes particularly problematic in precision agriculture, where accurate field-specific
540 knowledge has to be extracted from the synthesized near-infrared channel through precise image
541 processing. In this work, we proposed a novel approach for translating visual to near-infrared im-
542 ages, utilizing the robustness of Vegetation Indices (VIs), to synthesize valuable data for relative
543 precision agriculture operations. The proposed method relies on including an additional branch
544 in the GAN architecture, responsible for estimating the NDVI index from the translated near-
545 infrared channel and the RGB input. Via the backpropagated loss of this additional branch, the
546 semantic information enclosed in the NDVI representation is implanted in the translation process
547 and forces the network to generate realistic near-infrared images that accurately adhere to the
548 spectral characteristics of the targeted domain. The proposed modification is model-agnostic
549 and can be easily deployed in common GAN architectures while preserving the network’s abil-
550 ity to be end-to-end trainable. The efficiency of our method has been validated extensively by
551 modifying two different GAN architectures and measuring the quality of the translated results.
552 Additionally, the ability of the proposed approach to possess translation consistency and preserve
553 the semantic context of the scene was evaluated by semantically segmenting the synthesized
554 near-infrared data. In all cases, the proposed approach outperformed the other methods, con-
555 firming its efficiency in maintaining the semantic context and achieving meaningful and accurate
556 translations of visual to near-infrared images. These results demonstrate that our approach can
557 be effectively utilized to generate valuable near-infrared data that can be further processed by
558 corresponding field-specific applications.

559 The presented method can be extended in the future in several directions. The additional
560 branch calculating NDVI index can be upgraded with more VIs in order to enhance the VI-related
561 semantic information that is enclosed in the translation process. Furthermore, experiments
562 can be conducted by fusing the estimated NDVI representation at multiple stages of the GAN

563 generator, aiming to enhance the contribution of the NDVI-based features. Finally, different
564 loss functions and formulations of the corresponding objective function can be tested, aiming to
565 improve the translation accuracy and further examine the contribution of each network branch
566 to the translation task.

567 **Acknowledgments**

568 This research has been financed by the European Regional Development Fund of the Euro-
569 pean Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, En-
570 trepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH - CREATE - INNOVATE (T1EDK-
571 00636).

572 **References**

- 573 [1] B. Su, H. Chen, P. Chen, G. Bian, K. Liu, W. Liu, Deep learning-based solar-cell man-
574 ufacturing defect detection with complementary attention network, *IEEE Transactions on*
575 *Industrial Informatics* 17 (6) (2020) 4084–4095.
- 576 [2] P. Zhang, W. Liu, H. Wang, Y. Lei, H. Lu, Deep gated attention networks for large-scale
577 street-level scene segmentation, *Pattern Recognition* 88 (2019) 702–714.
- 578 [3] A. S. Lundervold, A. Lundervold, An overview of deep learning in medical imaging focusing
579 on mri, *Zeitschrift für Medizinische Physik* 29 (2) (2019) 102–127.
- 580 [4] J. Cai, Y. Zhang, L. Yang, H. Cai, S. Li, A context-augmented deep learning approach
581 for worker trajectory prediction on unstructured and dynamic construction sites, *Advanced*
582 *Engineering Informatics* 46 (2020) 101173.
- 583 [5] L. Lopez-Fuentes, J. van de Weijer, M. Bolanos, H. Skinnemoen, Multi-modal deep learning
584 approach for flood detection., *MediaEval* 17 (2017) 13–15.
- 585 [6] L. Deng, Z. Mao, X. Li, Z. Hu, F. Duan, Y. Yan, Uav-based multispectral remote sens-
586 ing for precision agriculture: A comparison between different cameras, *ISPRS journal of*
587 *photogrammetry and remote sensing* 146 (2018) 124–136.
- 588 [7] R. Kemker, C. Salvaggio, C. Kanan, Algorithms for semantic segmentation of multispectral
589 remote sensing imagery using deep learning, *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote*
590 *sensing* 145 (2018) 60–77.

- 591 [8] C. Li, D. Song, R. Tong, M. Tang, Illumination-aware faster r-cnn for robust multispectral
592 pedestrian detection, *Pattern Recognition* 85 (2019) 161–171.
- 593 [9] J. Kim, S. Kim, C. Ju, H. I. Son, Unmanned aerial vehicles in agriculture: A review of
594 perspective of platform, control, and applications, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 105100–105115.
- 595 [10] M. Zhang, T. Chen, X. Gu, Y. Kuai, C. Wang, D. Chen, C. Zhao, Uav-borne hyperspec-
596 tral estimation of nitrogen content in tobacco leaves based on ensemble learning methods,
597 *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 211 (2023) 108008.
- 598 [11] M. Hassanein, M. Khedr, N. El-Sheimy, Crop row detection procedure using low-cost uav
599 imagery system, *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and*
600 *Spatial Information Sciences* 42 (2019) 349–356.
- 601 [12] H. M. Sahin, T. Miftahushudur, B. Grieve, H. Yin, Segmentation of weeds and crops using
602 multispectral imaging and crf-enhanced u-net, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*
603 211 (2023) 107956.
- 604 [13] Y. Guo, J. Zhang, C. Yin, X. Hu, Y. Zou, Z. Xue, W. Wang, Plant disease identification
605 based on deep learning algorithm in smart farming, *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*
606 2020 (2020) 1–11.
- 607 [14] E. K. Raptis, M. Krestenitis, K. Egglezos, O. Kypris, K. Ioannidis, L. Doitsidis, A. C.
608 Kapoutsis, S. Vrochidis, I. Kompatsiaris, E. B. Kosmatopoulos, End-to-end precision agri-
609 culture uav-based functionalities tailored to field characteristics, *Journal of Intelligent &*
610 *Robotic Systems* 107 (2) (2023) 23.
- 611 [15] P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, P. Sarigiannidis, T. Lagkas, I. Moscholios, A compilation of uav
612 applications for precision agriculture, *Computer Networks* 172 (2020) 107148.
- 613 [16] D. J. Mulla, Twenty five years of remote sensing in precision agriculture: Key advances and
614 remaining knowledge gaps, *Biosystems engineering* 114 (4) (2013) 358–371.
- 615 [17] S. Chung, L. E. Breshears, J.-Y. Yoon, Smartphone near infrared monitoring of plant stress,
616 *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 154 (2018) 93–98.
- 617 [18] J. W. Rouse, R. H. Haas, J. A. Schell, D. W. Deering, et al., Monitoring vegetation systems
618 in the great plains with erts, *NASA special publication* 351 (1974) (1974) 309.

- 619 [19] P. Isola, J.-Y. Zhu, T. Zhou, A. A. Efros, Image-to-image translation with conditional
620 adversarial networks, in: Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern
621 recognition, 2017, pp. 1125–1134.
- 622 [20] J.-Y. Zhu, T. Park, P. Isola, A. A. Efros, Unpaired image-to-image translation using cycle-
623 consistent adversarial networks, in: Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on
624 computer vision, 2017, pp. 2223–2232.
- 625 [21] I. J. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair,
626 A. Courville, Y. Bengio, Generative adversarial networks, arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.2661
627 (2014).
- 628 [22] A. Radford, L. Metz, S. Chintala, Unsupervised representation learning with deep convolu-
629 tional generative adversarial networks, arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.06434 (2015).
- 630 [23] T.-C. Wang, M.-Y. Liu, J.-Y. Zhu, A. Tao, J. Kautz, B. Catanzaro, High-resolution image
631 synthesis and semantic manipulation with conditional gans, in: Proceedings of the IEEE
632 conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2018, pp. 8798–8807.
- 633 [24] J.-Y. Zhu, R. Zhang, D. Pathak, T. Darrell, A. A. Efros, O. Wang, E. Shechtman, Toward
634 multimodal image-to-image translation, arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.11586 (2017).
- 635 [25] Z. Yi, H. Zhang, P. Tan, M. Gong, Dualgan: Unsupervised dual learning for image-to-image
636 translation, in: Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision, 2017,
637 pp. 2849–2857.
- 638 [26] M.-Y. Liu, T. Breuel, J. Kautz, Unsupervised image-to-image translation networks, in:
639 Advances in neural information processing systems, 2017, pp. 700–708.
- 640 [27] X. Huang, M.-Y. Liu, S. Belongie, J. Kautz, Multimodal unsupervised image-to-image trans-
641 lation, in: Proceedings of the European conference on computer vision (ECCV), 2018, pp.
642 172–189.
- 643 [28] A. Anoosheh, E. Agustsson, R. Timofte, L. Van Gool, Combogan: Unrestrained scalability
644 for image domain translation, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision
645 and Pattern Recognition Workshops, 2018, pp. 783–790.

- 646 [29] Y. Choi, M. Choi, M. Kim, J.-W. Ha, S. Kim, J. Choo, Stargan: Unified generative adver-
647 sarial networks for multi-domain image-to-image translation, in: Proceedings of the IEEE
648 conference on computer vision and pattern recognition, 2018, pp. 8789–8797.
- 649 [30] Y. Fang, W. Deng, J. Du, J. Hu, Identity-aware cyclegan for face photo-sketch synthesis
650 and recognition, *Pattern Recognition* 102 (2020) 107249.
- 651 [31] L. Yan, W. Zheng, C. Gou, F.-Y. Wang, Isgan: Identity-sensitive generative adversarial
652 network for face photo-sketch synthesis, *Pattern Recognition* (2021) 108077.
- 653 [32] B. Bozorgtabar, D. Mahapatra, J.-P. Thiran, Exprada: Adversarial domain adaptation for
654 facial expression analysis, *Pattern Recognition* 100 (2020) 107111.
- 655 [33] A. Odena, C. Olah, J. Shlens, Conditional image synthesis with auxiliary classifier gans, in:
656 International conference on machine learning, PMLR, 2017, pp. 2642–2651.
- 657 [34] S.-W. Huang, C.-T. Lin, S.-P. Chen, Y.-Y. Wu, P.-H. Hsu, S.-H. Lai, Auggan: Cross domain
658 adaptation with gan-based data augmentation, in: Proceedings of the European Conference
659 on Computer Vision (ECCV), 2018, pp. 718–731.
- 660 [35] Z. Murez, S. Kolouri, D. Kriegman, R. Ramamoorthi, K. Kim, Image to image translation
661 for domain adaptation, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and
662 Pattern Recognition, 2018, pp. 4500–4509.
- 663 [36] M. Limmer, H. P. Lensch, Infrared colorization using deep convolutional neural networks, in:
664 2016 15th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA),
665 IEEE, 2016, pp. 61–68.
- 666 [37] P. L. Suárez, A. D. Sappa, B. X. Vintimilla, Infrared image colorization based on a triplet
667 degan architecture, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern
668 Recognition Workshops, 2017, pp. 18–23.
- 669 [38] Z. Dong, S.-i. Kamata, T. P. Breckon, Infrared image colorization using a s-shape network,
670 in: 2018 25th IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP), IEEE, 2018, pp.
671 2242–2246.
- 672 [39] X. Kuang, J. Zhu, X. Sui, Y. Liu, C. Liu, Q. Chen, G. Gu, Thermal infrared colorization
673 via conditional generative adversarial network, *Infrared Physics & Technology* 107 (2020)
674 103338.

- 675 [40] A. Mehri, A. D. Sappa, Colorizing near infrared images through a cyclic adversarial approach
676 of unpaired samples, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and
677 Pattern Recognition Workshops, 2019, pp. 0–0.
- 678 [41] T. Sun, C. Jung, Q. Fu, Q. Han, Nir to rgb domain translation using asymmetric cycle
679 generative adversarial networks, *IEEE Access* 7 (2019) 112459–112469.
- 680 [42] H. Dou, C. Chen, X. Hu, S. Peng, Asymmetric cyclegan for unpaired nir-to-rgb face image
681 translation, in: ICASSP 2019-2019 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech
682 and Signal Processing (ICASSP), IEEE, 2019, pp. 1757–1761.
- 683 [43] P. Perera, M. Abavisani, V. M. Patel, In2i: Unsupervised multi-image-to-image translation
684 using generative adversarial networks, in: 2018 24th International Conference on Pattern
685 Recognition (ICPR), IEEE, 2018, pp. 140–146.
- 686 [44] P. Li, M. Yang, Semantic gan: Application for cross-domain image style transfer, in: 2019
687 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME), IEEE, 2019, pp. 910–915.
- 688 [45] P. L. Suarez, A. D. Sappa, B. X. Vintimilla, Learning image vegetation index through a
689 conditional generative adversarial network, in: 2017 IEEE second Ecuador technical chapters
690 meeting (ETCM), IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- 691 [46] P. L. Suárez, A. D. Sappa, B. X. Vintimilla, Vegetation index estimation from monospectral
692 images, in: International Conference Image Analysis and Recognition, Springer, 2018, pp.
693 353–362.
- 694 [47] X. Yuan, J. Tian, P. Reinartz, Generating artificial near infrared spectral band from rgb im-
695 age using conditional generative adversarial network, *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry,
696 Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* 3 (2020) 279–285.
- 697 [48] P. L. Suárez, A. D. Sappa, B. X. Vintimilla, R. I. Hammoud, Image vegetation index through
698 a cycle generative adversarial network, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on
699 Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops, 2019, pp. 0–0.
- 700 [49] P. L. Suárez, A. D. Sappa, B. X. Vintimilla, Cycle generative adversarial network: Towards
701 a low-cost vegetation index estimation, in: 2021 IEEE International Conference on Image
702 Processing (ICIP), IEEE, 2021, pp. 2783–2787.

- 703 [50] H. Kerdegari, M. Razaak, V. Argyriou, P. Remagnino, Semi-supervised gan for classification
704 of multispectral imagery acquired by uavs, arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.10920 (2019).
- 705 [51] W. Zhao, W. Yamada, T. Li, M. Digman, T. Runge, Augmenting crop detection for preci-
706 sion agriculture with deep visual transfer learning—a case study of bale detection, *Remote*
707 *Sensing* 13 (1) (2021) 23.
- 708 [52] M. Fawakherji, C. Potena, A. Pretto, D. D. Bloisi, D. Nardi, Multi-spectral image synthesis
709 for crop/weed segmentation in precision farming, *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* 146
710 (2021) 103861.
- 711 [53] A. Singh, L. Bruzzone, Sigan: Spectral index generative adversarial network for data aug-
712 mentation in multispectral remote sensing images, *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing*
713 *Letters* (2021).
- 714 [54] H. Sheng, X. Chen, J. Su, R. Rajagopal, A. Ng, Effective data fusion with generalized
715 vegetation index: Evidence from land cover segmentation in agriculture, in: *Proceedings of*
716 *the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, 2020,
717 pp. 60–61.
- 718 [55] M. T. Chiu, X. Xu, Y. Wei, Z. Huang, A. G. Schwing, R. Brunner, H. Khachatryan, H. Kara-
719 petyan, I. Dozier, G. Rose, et al., Agriculture-vision: A large aerial image database for
720 agricultural pattern analysis, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer*
721 *Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020, pp. 2828–2838.
- 722 [56] M. Brown, S. Süsstrunk, Multi-spectral sift for scene category recognition, in: *CVPR 2011,*
723 *IEEE*, 2011, pp. 177–184.
- 724 [57] A. Gitelson, R. Stark, U. Grits, D. Rundquist, Y. Kaufman, D. Derry, Vegetation and soil
725 lines in visible spectral space: a concept and technique for remote estimation of vegetation
726 fraction, *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 23 (13) (2002) 2537–2562.
- 727 [58] M. Louhaichi, M. M. Borman, D. E. Johnson, Spatially located platform and aerial photog-
728 raphy for documentation of grazing impacts on wheat, *Geocarto International* 16 (1) (2001)
729 65–70.
- 730 [59] A. Bannari, D. Morin, F. Bonn, A. Huete, A review of vegetation indices, *Remote sensing*
731 *reviews* 13 (1-2) (1995) 95–120.

- 732 [60] J. Xue, B. Su, Significant remote sensing vegetation indices: A review of developments and
733 applications, *Journal of sensors* 2017 (1) (2017) 1353691.
- 734 [61] A. Karnieli, N. Agam, R. T. Pinker, M. Anderson, M. L. Imhoff, G. G. Gutman, N. Panov,
735 A. Goldberg, Use of ndvi and land surface temperature for drought assessment: Merits and
736 limitations, *Journal of climate* 23 (3) (2010) 618–633.
- 737 [62] D. Pathak, P. Krahenbuhl, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, A. A. Efros, Context encoders: Feature
738 learning by inpainting, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and
739 pattern recognition*, 2016, pp. 2536–2544.
- 740 [63] L. Zhao, H. Bai, J. Liang, B. Zeng, A. Wang, Y. Zhao, Simultaneous color-depth super-
741 resolution with conditional generative adversarial networks, *Pattern Recognition* 88 (2019)
742 356–369.
- 743 [64] S. Xiang, H. Li, On the effects of batch and weight normalization in generative adversarial
744 networks, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.03971* (2017).
- 745 [65] D. Ulyanov, A. Vedaldi, V. Lempitsky, Improved texture networks: Maximizing quality
746 and diversity in feed-forward stylization and texture synthesis, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE
747 Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2017, pp. 6924–6932.
- 748 [66] L.-C. Chen, Y. Zhu, G. Papandreou, F. Schroff, H. Adam, Encoder-decoder with atrous
749 separable convolution for semantic image segmentation, in: *Proceedings of the European
750 conference on computer vision (ECCV)*, 2018, pp. 801–818.
- 751 [67] G. P. Asner, Biophysical and biochemical sources of variability in canopy reflectance, *Remote
752 sensing of Environment* 64 (3) (1998) 234–253.
- 753 [68] B.-C. Gao, Ndw_i—a normalized difference water index for remote sensing of vegetation
754 liquid water from space, *Remote sensing of environment* 58 (3) (1996) 257–266.
- 755 [69] A. Huete, K. Didan, T. Miura, E. P. Rodriguez, X. Gao, L. G. Ferreira, Overview of the
756 radiometric and biophysical performance of the modis vegetation indices, *Remote sensing
757 of environment* 83 (1-2) (2002) 195–213.